

Clicking Towards a Cure: CIC-39, a Modulator of Store-Operated Calcium Entry in Rare Genetic Myopathies

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Approches in Our Laboratory

Deuteration

Nat. Rev. Drug Discov. **2023**, 552-584

Soft Drug

J. Med. Chem. **2018**, 61, 4436-4455

PROTACs

J. Med. Chem. **2022**, 65, 15282-15299

Photocatalysis

J. Org. Chem. **2024**, 89, 633-643

Multicomponent Reactions

Eur. J. Med. Chem. **2024**, 279, 116845

Click Chemistry

“The reaction must be modular, wide in scope, give very high yields, generate only inoffensive by-products that can be removed by non-chromatographic methods, and be stereospecific (but not necessarily enantioselective). The required process characteristics include simple reaction conditions, readily available starting materials and reagents, the use of no solvents or a solvent that is benign (such as water) or easily removed, and simple product isolation.”

K. Barry Sharpless

Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2001**, 113, 2056

1. CuAAC, 2002

Cu-Catalyzed Alkyne-Azide Cycloaddition

Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2002**, 41, 2596

J. Org. Chem. **2002**, 67, 3057

2. SPAAC, 2010

Strain-promoted Azide-Alkyne Click Chemistry reaction

JACS, **2010**, 132, 3688

3. SuFEx, 2014

Sulfur (VI) Fluoride exchange

Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. **2014**, 53,9430

CuAAC as a Linking Strategy

Cu-Catalyzed Alkyne-Azide Cycloaddition (CuAAC)

1. Bioconjugation: ADCs

sacituzumab govitecan
Trodelvy®

2. PROTACs

J. Med. Chem. **2018**, 61, 453

J. Med. Chem. **2018**, 61, 482

For a review: ChemMedChem, **2023**, 18, e202300422; RSC Chem. Biol. **2024**, 5, 189

For a review: ChemBioChem **2022**, 23, e202200016

CuAAC in the Discovery of Hit Compounds

- Strong dipole moment, planar and aromatic character, 2HBA,1HBD
- Isostere of *trans*-amide
- Chemical and metabolic stability
- Negligible CYP inhibition
- Generation of new IP

Review > Med Res Rev. 2008 Mar;28(2):278-308. doi: 10.1002/med.20107.

Click chemistry reactions in medicinal chemistry: applications of the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition between azides and alkynes

Gian Cesare Tron¹, Tracey Pirali, Richard A Billington, Pier Luigi Canonico, Giovanni Sorba, Armando A Genazzani

Affiliations + expand

PMID: 17763363 DOI: 10.1002/med.20107

> ChemMedChem. 2014 Nov;9(11):2497-508. doi: 10.1002/cmdc.201402233. Epub 2014 Jul 30.

Are 1,4- and 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles good pharmacophoric groups?

Alberto Massarotti¹, Silvio Aprile, Valentina Mercalli, Erika Del Grosso, Giorgio Grosa, Giovanni Sorba, Gian Cesare Tron

Affiliations + expand

PMID: 25079879 DOI: 10.1002/cmdc.201402233

Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry
Volume 134, 2021, Pages 101-148

Chapter Three - Click 1,2,3-triazoles in drug discovery and development: From the flask to the clinic?

Marta Serafini, Tracey Pirali, Gian Cesare Tron

CuAAC in Our Laboratory Over the Years

HDAC inhibitors

J. Comb. Chem. **2008**, *10*, 624

Org. Lett. **2006**, *8*, 4145-4148
Mol. Divers. **2010**, *14*, 109-121

Estradiol and Resveratrol Analogues

J. Med. Chem. **2006**, *49*, 467-470
ChemMedChem **2007**, *2*, 437-440

Click Chemistry

Med. Res. Rev. **2008**, *28*, 278

Tubulin inhibitors

Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett. **2011**, *21*, 764

PI3K Inhibitors

WO 2012073184 A1 20120607
ChemMedChem **2017**, *12*, 1542
Nat. Commun. **2018**, *9*, 5232

CuAAC is Not a Panacea

Small molecules discovered by click chemistry:

Thousands at preclinical stage

A few in clinical trials

None on the market

Drawbacks:

1. Low aqueous solubility

2. Explosivity of azides

3. Copper-related safety concerns

JOC The Journal of Organic Chemistry

pubs.acs.org/joc

Editorial

How Dangerous Is Too Dangerous? A Perspective on Azide Chemistry

Cite This: *J. Org. Chem.* 2022, 87, 11293–11295

[Read Online](#)

Store-Operated Calcium Entry - SOCE

Dionysus leading the Horae
- neo-Attic Roman relief, 1st century -

Orai1: the gatekeeper of Ca²⁺ entryways into cells

SOCE: Physiological and Pathophysiological Role

Skeletal muscle: Effective contraction over time

Platelet: Activation

Immune cells: T cell differentiation

Pancreatic acinar cells: Digestive enzyme secretion

SOCE over-activation: Ca²⁺ overload

Transversal mechanism in many diseases

Autoimmune disorders

- Multiple Sclerosis
- Lupus
- Rheumatoid Arthritis

Rare genetic myopathies

Tubular aggregate myopathy

Duchenne muscular dystrophy

Acute Pancreatitis

SOCE: an Under-Explored Target

Drug	Company	Therapeutic indication	Phase	Status	Reference
CM4620 (Auxora)	CalciMedica	Pancreatitis due to Asparaginase	I/II	Recruiting	NCT04195347
CM4620 (Auxora)	CalciMedica	Acute Pancreatitis	II	Completed	NCT03709342
CM4620 (Auxora)	CalciMedica	Acute Pancreatitis and Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome	II II	Completed	NCT04681066 NCT03401190 Bruen C., et al. 2021
CM4620 (Auxora)	CalciMedica	Severe COVID-19 Pneumonia	II II	Completed	NCT04661540 NCT04345614 Bruen C., et al. 2022 Miller J., et al. 2020
CM4620 (Auxora)	CalciMedica	High- Risk Patients With Critical COVID-19 Pneumonia	II	Withdrawn (lack of sufficient numbers of critically ill patients)	NCT05171920
RP3128	Rizhen Pharmaceuticals	Asthma	II	Terminated (significant recruitment delay in PoC part)	NCT02958982 Barde J., et al. 2021
RP4010	Rizhen Pharmaceuticals	Relapsed or Refractory Lymphomas	I/Ib	Terminated (study stopped after reviewing PK and safety results))	NCT03119467 Barde J., et al. 2021
PRCL-2	PRCL Research Inc.	Plaque Psoriasis	I IIa	Completed	NCT03062618 NCT03614078

Two Libraries of SOCE Modulators by CuAAC

- All SOCE modulators share the arylamide moiety
- Poor structural information on Orai1

Pyr6

Bioisosteric replacement

1st library: pytriazoles

WO 2017/212414 A1
J. Med. Chem. **2018**, 61, 9756

Synta66

Bioisosteric replacement

2nd library: biphenyltriazoles

WO 2021/165735 A1
J. Med. Chem. **2020**, 63, 14761

Screening by calcium imaging

++ CIC-39Na: Activity on SOCE, Selectivity and Drug-Likeness

Cell viability

No cytotoxicity up to 60 μ M

Activity on SOCE

IC₅₀: 851 \pm 54 nM

Selectivity over other channels

No inhibition of:
VOCCs
TRPM8
TRPV1

H₂O solubility

3.6 mg/mL

In vitro metabolic stability

60', MLM: 75%

In vivo PK (mice, 10 mg/Kg, iv)

t_{1/2}: 10.3 h

WO 2021/165735 A1
J. Med. Chem. **2020**, 63, 14761

In vivo efficacy in acute pancreatitis

10 mg/kg ip x2

++ First Indication: Tubular Aggregate Myopathy - TAM

- **Ultra-rare genetic disease**
Global prevalence 1/100,000
- No patient registries
- Ab. 50 families reported in literature
- **Multi-organ, progressive and chronic disorder** that mainly affects **muscles and platelets**
- Histological hallmark: **tubular aggregates**
- Clinical hallmarks:
 - **Cramps & muscle weakness**
 - **Thrombocytopenia & abnormal bleeding**
 - Additional multisystemic signs

NO approved therapy

NO therapy in clinical trials

Gain-of-function Mutations of Orai1 and STIM1

STIM1/ORAI1 gain-of-function mutations

Tubular aggregate myopathies

Tubular aggregate myopathy
York platelet syndrome
Stormorken syndrome

Overactivated SOCE
Ca²⁺

- Autosomal, dominant and missense mutations: constitutive activation of SOCE
- Poor genotype-phenotype correlation

Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci. **2015**, 1356, 45
Human. Mutat. **2020**, 41, 17

Heterologous systems

GoF Mutations	SOCE Inhibition % (CIC-39 3 μ M)
STIM1p.D84E	93.8 \pm 2.2
STIM1 p.K104N	91.4 \pm 2.9
STIM1 p.F108I	81.7 \pm 3.3
STIM1 p.H109R	82.7 \pm 2.3
STIM1 p.I115F	82.5 \pm 3.5
STIM1 p.V138I	62.8 \pm 6.2
STIM1 p.S630F	85.9 \pm 2.2
STIM1 p.R749H	92.9 \pm 6.9
ORAI1 p.P245L	98.2 \pm 2.3
ORAI1 p.G98S	76.6 \pm 6.6
ORAI1 p.S97C	78.7 \pm 4.6

Cell Calcium, **2022**, 105, 102605

Patients' fibroblasts

GoF Mutations	SOCE Inhibition % (CIC-39 3 μ M)
STIM1p.G81D	62.6 \pm 4.2
STIM1 p.S88G	77.4 \pm 3.8
STIM1 p.R304Q	32.7 \pm 1.6

Knock-in Mouse Model for TAM

KI-STIM1^{I115F}: clinically relevant point mutation located in an EF-hand motif of STIM1

- Viable and fertile colony
- Platelet dysfunction
- Muscle weakness
- Muscle degeneration

Dis. Model Mech. 2020, 13, 041111

++ Intrapерitoneal Micropumps

- Continuous and controlled release (average plasma concentration: $251 \mu\text{g/L}$)
- Constant dosage (no overdose / underdose)
- No external connections
- No frequent animal handling

Tubular Aggregate Myopathy – *in vivo* data

Increase of platelet number and reduction of blood loss

CIC-39: 60 mg/Kg/daily 15 days
Administration by intraperitoneal minipumps

Blood Adv. **2022**, 6,4471

Increase of power

CIC-39: 60 mg/Kg/daily 56 days
Administration by intraperitoneal minipumps

Treadmill test

KI-STIM1^{I115F}

Reduction of tubular aggregates

CIC-39: 60 mg/Kg/daily 56 days
Administration by intraperitoneal minipumps

Manuscript in preparation

ORPHAN DRUG DESIGNATION

Second Indication: Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy - DMD

- **Rare disease**
Global prevalence 5/100,000 males
- **Severe and progressive** X-linked recessive disorder
- Loss-of-function nonsense mutations/deletions in the **dystrophin gene**
- Progressive **muscle weakness, degeneration and wasting**
- **Muscle fibrosis and inflammation**
- **Loss of deambulation and premature death** due to heart and/or respiratory failure

Controversial efficacy of existing therapies:

- **Stop codon readthrough** (ataluren) not approved by FDA and withdrawn by EMA
- **Exon skipping** (ASOs: eteplirsen, casimersen, golodirsen) approved by FDA, not by EMA
- **HDAC inhibitor** (givinostat) approved by FDA, under evaluation by EMA
- **Gene therapy** (Elevidys) approved by FDA, not by EMA

SOCE: Novel Target for DMD Treatment

> Hum Mol Genet. 2014 Jul 15;23(14):3706-15. doi: 10.1093/hmg/ddu079. Epub 2014 Feb 20.

Enhanced Ca²⁺ influx from STIM1-Orai1 induces muscle pathology in mouse models of muscular dystrophy

Sanjeeva A Goonasekera¹, Jennifer Davis¹, Jennifer Q Kwong¹, Federica Accornero¹, Lan Wei-LaPierre², Michelle A Sargent¹, Robert T Dirksen², Jeffery D Molkentin³

> Arch Biochem Biophys. 2015 Mar 1;569:1-9. doi: 10.1016/j.abb.2015.01.025. Epub 2015 Feb 4.

Store-operated calcium entry contributes to abnormal Ca²⁺ signalling in dystrophic mdx mouse myoblasts

Marta Onopiuk¹, Wojciech Brutkowski², Christopher Young³, Elżbieta Krasowska², Justyna Róg⁴, Morten Ritso⁵, Sylwia Wojciechowska⁴, Stephen Arkle³, Krzysztof Zabłocki⁶, Dariusz C Górecki³

> J Gen Physiol. 2022 Sep 5;154(9):e202213081. doi: 10.1085/jgp.202213081. Epub 2022 Aug 8.

Postdevelopmental knockout of Orai1 improves muscle pathology in a mouse model of Duchenne muscular dystrophy

Maricela García-Castañeda¹, Antonio Michelucci^{1,2}, Nan Zhao¹, Sundeep Malik¹, Robert T Dirksen¹

SOCE Overactivation in *mdx* Myotubes

Traces= average of 120 cells from 3 different experiments

SOCE over-activation in myotubes from DMD mouse model (*mdx*)
CIC-39 reduces SOCE restoring Ca^{2+} to physiological levels

Experimental Design in *mdx*

- Sacrifice**
- Apoptotic/Necrotic cell count
 - Histological analysis
 - Organ harvesting
 - Muscle harvesting

- 4 experimental groups:**
- WT Vehicle (n = 8)
 - WT CIC-39 (n = 8)
 - *mdx* Vehicle (n = 8)
 - *mdx* CIC-39 (n = 8)

CIC-39 in its salified form 60 mg/Kg
(plasma concentration corresponding to the IC₅₀ in *in vitro* models)

Results in *mdx*: Muscle

mdx

CIC-39 reduces CK plasma levels

CIC-39: 60 mg/Kg/daily 60 days
Administration by intraperitoneal minipumps

**** $P < 0.0001$ *mdx* CIC-39 vs *mdx*

CIC-39 increases muscle strength

Grip strength test

* $P = 0.0027$; *** $P = 0.0001$ *mdx* CIC-39 vs *mdx*

CIC-39 decreases apoptosis and necrosis

Manuscript in preparation

ORPHAN DRUG DESIGNATION

Results in *mdx*: Pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic biomarkers

Inflammation

Anova test followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. ****P < 0.0001; **P ≤ 0.005, *P ≤ 0.0191 mdx vehicle vs mdx CIC-39, WT vehicle, WT CIC-39

Diaphragm

Fibrosis

Anova test followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. **P = 0.0037, ****P < 0.0001 mdx vehicle vs mdx CIC-39, WT vehicle, WT CIC-39

CIC-39 Efficacy in DMD patient with Point Mutation 64 (MIOFIN 195, Age 1)

Myotubes

SOCE evaluation (single cell calcium imaging)

P = 0.0298; #### P ≤ 0.0041;
P = 0.0006 vs Vehicle
Kruskal Wallis non-parametric test

P ≤ 0.0409; ### P = 0.0004 vs Vehicle
Kruskal Wallis non-parametric test

Average Ca²⁺-levels of approximately 300 cells from eight separate coverslips performed on 2 separate days.

CIC-39 modulates over-activated SOCE in myotubes in a concentration dependent manner

Gene expression evaluation (qRT-PCR) 72h of CIC-39 treatment

* P ≤ 0.0386; *** P ≤ 0.0006; **** P = 0.0001 vs HV (Healthy volunteer)
≤ 0.046; ## < 0.0082; ### < 0.0004 vs Vehicle
Kruskal Wallis non-parametric test
n = 6 technical replicates from two experiments.

fibrosis
inflammation

CIC-39 reduces pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic biomarkers expression in myotubes

CIC-39 Efficacy in DMD patient with Point Mutation 64 (MIOFIN 195, Age 13 yo)

PBMCs

SOCE evaluation (fluorometric assay)

CIC-39 modulates over-activated SOCE

TNFα release (cytofluorimetric assay)

CIC-39 reduces inflammation by modulating TNFα

Gene expression evaluation (qRT-PCR)

72h of CIC-39 treatment

CIC-39 reduces pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic biomarkers expression in PBMCs

Good safety profile

Not genotoxic and mutagenic

- **No micronuclei induction** in human lymphocytes
- **No induction of reverse mutation** by Ames test

Not cardiotoxic (*h*ERG channel test)

No significant inhibition of *h*ERG channel
(only 2% at 1 μ M)

Good pharmacokinetic profile

(mice, 10 mg/Kg, i.v.)

$t_{1/2}$ = 10.3 h
 Clearance = 0.43 L/h/kg
 V_d = 6.49 L/kg
 C_{max} = 16248.79 μ g/L

Good bioavailability

(in rats and minipigs)

Oral Bioavailability = 80%
 Comparative PK analysis based on intravenous and oral administration

Tolerability

Two-week oral toxicity study in rats
 (daily oral administration, 60, 180 and 300 mg/Kg)

No abnormalities (mortality, clinical signs, body weight reduction)

MTD > 300 mg/Kg

- **Repeated-dose toxicology studies** in rats and minipigs (4-week oral treatment followed by a 2 week recovery period)
- **Safety pharmacology** (e.g., Effects on the cardiovascular and respiratory function)
- Characterization of **SOCE over-activation** in a **wide cohort** of DMD patients bearing different mutations
- **Effect of CIC-39** on SOCE over-activation, inflammation and fibrosis in a **wide cohort** of DMD patients bearing different mutations

- Discovered by click chemistry
- Reduces SOCE over-activation
- Efficacy in transgenic models of TAM and DMD
- Efficacy in patients' samples
- Excellent oral bioavailability
- High tolerability

CIC-39 might represent a therapeutic option for TAM and DMD patients, regardless of the specific mutation

«Chemists are like everyone else, and they fall into the trap that fancy is better.

But I believed we could get just as much good function from simple molecules made by simple methods.

People laughed, it was not complicated enough»

- Beatrice Riva
- Luigi Azzarone
- Carlotta Muschitiello
- Maurizio Mariani
- Daniela Chicco
- Emanuele Gallo

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